

A STUDY ON HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS' EMOTIONAL MATURITY AND STUDY HABIT IN TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT

Dr. M. Rajakumar

Assistant Professor, Government College of Education, Gandhinagar, Katapdi,
Vellore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

The present investigation has been undertaken in order to study the Emotional Maturity and study habit of higher secondary students in Tirunelveli District. By using the simple random sampling technique 1060 higher secondary students were taken as sample. The tool used to find out the Emotional Maturity scale, by Roma pal (1964) and study habit inventory was constructed and validated by Patel 91975). The mean value of Emotional Maturity scores 136.53 indicates that the Higher Secondary Students are having extremely unstable Emotional Maturity. The mean value of study habit scores 142.12 indicates that higher secondary students are having good study habit

Emotional Maturity:

Performance in any Endeavour is largely contingent upon mental preparation, psychological strength and Emotional Maturity. Emotions are great motivating forces throughout the span of human life; affecting aspirations, actions and thoughts of an individual. Emotions are aroused by happenings or circumstances that enhance the gratification of a person need or the realization of high goal. The concept of 'mature' emotional behavior at any level reflects the fruits of normal emotional development. It is a psychological term used to indicate that a person responds to the circumstances or environment in an appropriate manner. Maturity implies putting away of childish thing and reading oneself as an adult ready shoulder responsibilities that develop upon one in general in worldly affairs. One's Emotional Maturity also plays a significant part determining whether one's ventures are successful or not.

Study Habit:

Study means to apply the minds to the acquisition learning whether by means of books or observation or experiment. Habits are acquired and not inborn. Habit is an accomplished form of behaviour in which the things are done quickly, accurately, automatically with little voluntary attention.

Study implies investigation for the mastery of facts, ideas or procedures, that as yet is unknown or only partially known to the individual. Any application of energy directed towards the learning of new material, the solution of a problem the discovery of new problem of life. So formations of habits are very real needs for progress. It is found that new levels in achievement are possible by improving the study habits.

Need of the Study:

Successful students differ from the average ones. Some students who appear to study all the time just get by, while others who don't appear to put in as much time and effort do well. The truth is that success in school is not so much determined by sheer intelligence as knowing how to study. Higher Secondary Students are crossing the crucial adolescent period, in this period their study are affected much by their Emotional Maturity and Study Habit, hence the investigator decided to take up this study.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of this study are

- To find out the level of Emotional Maturity of Higher Secondary Students.
- To find out the study habit of higher secondary students.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between the selected pairs of sub samples in respective of Emotional Maturity of Higher Secondary Students.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between the selected pairs of sub samples in respective of higher secondary students' study habit.

Hypothesis:

Suitable hypothesis were framed.

Method of Study:

The present investigation was undertaken by using normative survey method.

Statistical Techniques:

In this present investigation the following statistical techniques were framed.

Descriptive Analysis:

- Measures of central tendency (Mean)

- Measures of variability (Standard Deviation)

Differential Analysis

Independent sample 't' test

Sample of the Study:

The present study consists of 1060 higher secondary students studying in Tirunelveli district of Tamilnadu state. The sample was selected by using simple random sampling technique. The sample forms a representative sample of the entire population. Due proportionate weightage was given to various subs – samples.

Descriptive and Differential Analysis:

Analysis of Mean and SD scores of Emotional Maturity of Higher Secondary Students

To find out the Emotional Maturity of higher secondary students mean and SD are calculated

Table 1: Mean and SD scores of Emotional Maturity of Higher Secondary Students

Sample	N	Mean	SD
Entire sample	1060	136.53	24.46

The mean value of Emotional Maturity scores 136.53 indicates that the higher secondary students are having good family environment.

Analysis of Mean and SD scores of Study Habits of the Higher Secondary Students

To find out the study habit of higher secondary students mean SD (standard Deviation) are calculated.

Table 1: Mean and SD scores of Study Habits of the Higher Secondary Students

Sample	N	Mean	SD
Entire Sample	1060	142.12	23.90

The mean value of study habit scores 142.12 (63.16) indicates that the higher secondary students are having good study habit.

Analysis of mean and SD scores Emotional Maturity of the male and female higher secondary students

Null hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Table 2: The significance of the Difference between the Means of Emotional Maturity Scores of the Male and Female Students

Sub - Samples	N	Mean	SD	T - Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Male	460	132.48	26.84	4.76	Significant
Female	600	139.63	21.98		

From the above table, since the 't' value is significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference between the male and female higher secondary school students with respect to their family environment.

Analysis of mean and SD scores of Emotional Maturity of the rural and urban higher secondary students

Null hypothesis

There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Table 3: The Significance of the Difference between the Means of Emotional Maturity Scores of the Rural and Urban Students

Sub - Samples	N	Mean	SD	t - value	Significance at 0.05 level
Rural	560	135.18	26.75	1.92	Not Significant
Urban	500	138.04	21.52		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Analysis of Mean and SD Scores Emotional Maturity of the Government and Aided higher secondary students

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between government and aided higher secondary school students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Table 4: The Significance of the Difference between the Means of Emotional Maturity Scores of the Government and Aided Students

Sub - Samples	N	Mean	SD	t - value	Significance at 0.05 level
Govt.	571	136.77	24.045	0.34	Not significant
Aided	489	136.25	24.95		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between government and aided higher secondary school students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Analysis of Mean and SD scores of Emotional Maturity of the Nuclear and Joint Family Higher Secondary Students

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint Family Higher Secondary Students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Table 5: The significance of the Difference between the Means of Emotional Maturity Scores of the Nuclear and Joint Family Students

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t - value	Significance at 0.05 level
Nuclear	435	135.71	25.86	0.89	Not Significant
Joint	625	137.10	23.43		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint Family Higher Secondary Students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Analysis of Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Gender

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Male and Female Higher Secondary students with respect to their Study habit.

Table 3: Significance of difference between Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Gender

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Male	460	142.21	25.99	0.09	Not significant
Female	600	142.06	22.19		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the male and female Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Study habit.

Analysis of Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Locality

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary students with respect to their Study habit.

Table 4: Significance of difference between Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Locality

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S D	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Rural	560	141.10	24.16	1.48	Not significant
Urban	500	143.27	23.58		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary students with respect to their Study habit.

Analysis of Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to the Type of Institution

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Government and Aided Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Study habit.

Table 5: Significance of difference between Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to the Type of Institution

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Govt.	571	141.34	23.78	1.14	Not significant
Aided	489	146.03	24.04		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the Government and Aided Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Study habit.

Analysis of Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to their family type

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint family higher Secondary School students with respect to their Study habit.

Table 5: Significance of difference between Mean Study habit scores of higher secondary students with respect to their family type

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Nuclear	435	141.45	24.65	0.75	Not significant
Joint	625	142.59	23.38		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the Nuclear and Joint family Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Study habit.

Findings of the Study:

- The mean value of family environment scores indicates that the higher secondary students are having extremely unstable Emotional Maturity.
- There is significant difference between male and female higher secondary students with respect to level of Emotional Maturity.
- There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to level of Emotional Maturity.
- There is no significant difference between Government and Aided higher secondary school students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.
- There is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint Family Higher Secondary Students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.
- The mean value of study habit scores indicates that the higher secondary students are having good study habit.
- There is no significant difference between Male and Female Higher Secondary Students with respect to their Study habit.
- There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Students with respect to their Study habit.
- There is no significant difference between Government and Aided Higher Secondary School Students with respect to their Study habit.
- There is no significant difference between the Nuclear and Joint family Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Study habit.

Recommendations:

The result of this study shows that higher secondary students are having extremely unstable Emotional Maturity. Hence, to stabilize and to increase their Emotional, efforts are to be taken by the parents and Teachers. There is significant difference between male and female, Day scholar and Hosteller, higher secondary school students, with respect to their Emotional Maturity. From these results it is evident that these variables are influencing higher secondary students Emotional Maturity. Hence, these variables need to be considered by the parents and teachers. There is no significant difference between Government and Aided Higher Secondary School Students and rural and urban resisted students with respect to their Emotional Maturity.

Conclusions:

This study shows the nature of Emotional Maturity Study Habit of higher secondary students in Tirunelveli districts, particularly of Economics students. Further this study reveals the differences in influence by the demography of the students. To sustain and to increase good Emotional Maturity and good study habit, special concern is to be extended by the parents. Parents should be met by the teachers frequently report about students' Positive and negatives and needs.

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